

Table S1.3

	Bio03	Bio12	Bio15	Bio18	DEM	Slope
Combined	2.5424	31.33126	3.92612	36.1294	7.1108	18.96
Transition	2.9	32.41404	2.3266	31.23004	18.63114	13.68822
Maternity	5.44544	26.5663	5.24438	37.00218	17.89218	7.8495
Hibernacula	6.3935	21.87648	3.93754	14.21812	33.16678	20.40758
Ecoregion 1	0.9477221	1.02	0.95	1.0829572	0.99	1.01
Ecoregion 4	1.0209974	0.9800609	0.9911634	1.0046279	0.9990951	1.0043745
Ecoregion 5	1.0294416	0.9592813	1.0163638	1.0740889	0.9367018	0.9882539
Ecoregion 6	0.9836468	1.0191214	1.0132197	0.9971085	0.9681059	1.0195384
Ecoregion 8	1.0084914	0.9977668	0.9953172	0.9971383	0.9996223	1.0017008
Ecoregion 13	1.0104757	0.9038749	1.0089537	1.0182785	1.0493431	1.0132868
Ecoregion 14	1.0384014	0.8988841	1.0306774	1.0594201	0.9636364	1.0149783
Ecoregion 78	1.02604	1.002102	1.039116	0.89781	1.031864	1.007756
Ecoregion 85	0.8834957	1.1782754	1.0110559	0.8917618	1.1866096	0.8832556

Table S1.3. Contribution of each environmental predictor to the final model. For statewide models (Combined, Hibernacula, Maternity, and Transition), values indicate percent contribution to the model. For ecoregion-specific ensemble of small models output, values indicate proportional contribution of the variable in the final ensemble model. Value >1 indicates the focal variable has a higher contribution than average. Bold values indicate highest contributing variables.